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Marital Relations in the Movies ‘Ghare-Baire’ And ‘Astitva’: A Comparative Study

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“Marriages are made in Heaven, but so are thunder and lightning.”

Anonymous

Abstract:

The above stated quotation is very relevant in case of marriages. As marriage is not always a bed of roses but rather a Herculean task to manage. Every marriage is subject to one or another kind of misery, adjustment, domination, mute approval of the vice, endurance so on and so forth. It is always a matter of expectations and aspirations from the spouse. Denial of these leads to a fiasco, and marriage as an institution collapse. In the present paper, I have intended to deal under the context of comparative literature, with the marital or spousal relationships in the context of two movies dealing with extramarital relationships with different backgrounds, purposes, characters and the climaxes.

Keywords: Marriage, relationship, marital, movies, adultery.

Introduction

Comparative literature involves about analysing and comparing literary works from different cultures, languages and historical periods. Its focus is to identify similarities and differences, explore themes and intentions and to understand the cultural, social and historical contexts. It

also includes cultural studies, history, philosophy and print media. By doing comparative study one can gain knowledge and deeper understanding of the social and historical contexts.

Objective of writing this research paper

Marital relationship is now a very sensitive and worldwide phenomenon. People are now seriously considering about marriage as an institution. The objective of writing this paper is to study spousal relationships especially in the context of two movies; one Bengali movie, “*Ghare-Baire*” and another one Hindi movie, ‘*Astitva*’. The purpose is to analyze the marital relationships in these two movies comparing their cultural and social contexts. The intention behind selecting only these two movies lies in the fact that existence of a love triangle with particularly a wife engages into adultery.

Research Methodology

The descriptive method has been used for this paper. The primary sources, the critical reviews have been used for the purpose. The online websites, journals and books are referred for secondary data collection.

Review of Literature

- “The main characters talk, and the camera just stays on them and waits until they finish, yet these conversations in golden light and shadows have their own kind of voltage”. (Pauline Koel)
- Novel was praised by Tagore’s friends William Rothenstein and W.B. Yeats. A friend of Einstein’s advised him, “you must read- the finest novel I have read for a long time.”
- “Purity and grandeur.” (Hermann Hesse)
- “A wonderful book, strong and gentle.” (Bertolt Brecht)

- “Sandip resembles nothing so much as the conventional blackguard of the Indian stage or the Bombay cinema, stroking his handle bar moustache as he gloats over a bag of gold and a cowering maiden.” (Anita Desai)
- “Lord, Lord, how subject we men are to this vice of lying.” (W. Shakespear)

Satyajit Ray’s Bengali movie ‘*Ghare-Baire*’(1984)

The Bengali movie is based on a novel written by Rabindranath Tagore originally (*Ghare-Baire*) in 1915. Later on, translated into English by his nephew Surendranath Tagore. The movie is directed by Satyajit Ray. It has its political background. It is about ‘Swadeshi movement’, a reaction against Partition of Bengal executed by then Viceroy of India Lord Curzon in 1905. The nationalist movement ‘Swadeshi’ appealing for a boycott of foreign-made good mainly the British textile.

The story revolves around a couple Nikhil Choudhary, landlord (Victor Banerjee), his wife Bimala Choudhary (Swatilekha Chatterjee) and Nikhil’s friend, Sandip, a national revolutionist (Soumitra Chatterjee). They lead a happy married life until the arrival of radical and great nationalist orator, Sandip, who tries to fascinate Bimala and she succumbs to his vile intentions. After realizing his deceitful and lavish lifestyle, Bimala repents and Nikhil, a benevolent husband accepts her back into his life. Later, in a communal riot Nikhil passes away. Bimala leads a life of a lonely widow. Sandip flees away.

Mahesh Manjrekar’s Hindi Movie ‘*Astitva*’

Another movie in Hindi i.e, ‘*Astitva*’ is a saga of a woman’s quest for identity. The main themes of the movie are marriage and identity, extramarital affairs, spousal abuse and male chauvinism. The movie was written in 2000 by Imtiyaz Hussien and Mahesh Manjrekar. It does not have any political and literary background, but a remarkable attempt on the part of

Director and actors to make it appears on the scene. It is about male Chauvinist protagonism, extra-marital affair and spousal abuse. It's a love triangle of the husband, Shrikant (Sachin Khedekar), the wife, Aditi (Tabbu) and Malhar, the music teacher (Mohnish Behl). Shrikant is presented as a budding businessman, mostly on foreign tours, leaving his newly wedded wife all alone. In order to get rid of boredom, she asks him for the job. But his ego gets hurt and he refuses the proposal. To get out of ennui, she is allowed to take up for the music. Then the introduction of music teacher, Malhar Kamat takes place. In absence of Shrikant, Aditi is constantly under the feelings of yearning and abandonment. One day under the influence of rainy season, Aditi resolves to physical infatuation and commits adultery. Later she repents and tries hard to confess to her husband but all in vain. He doesn't listen to her as being over-joyed with good news of his fatherhood and a good contract for his company.

After some years Aditi receives a will of her master who left a great property in her name. the insect of suspicion enters into the mind of Shrikant and he scolds Aditi. Aditi reveals the truth. He abandons her. But she after taking out all which is simmering inside her walks away out of her house as a liberated woman.

Both the films won world acclaims and many national and international awards in their ages respectively.

'*Ghare-Baire*' was first released at the Cannes Film Festival in France on May 22, 1984 and was nominated for Golden Palm Award. It was released later in the United States on June 21, 1985.

Similarities in both the movies

The intention behind selecting these two movies is apparent from the fact that some themes are common. such as:

- Love triangulations.
- Extra-Marital relationships.

- Wife engaged in adultery.
- Illusion and realizations.

As discussed earlier, a love triangle prevails in both the movies. In '*Ghare-Baire*' a Bengali zamindar Nikhil marries Bimala of both lower status and darker complexion. they have idyllic love relationship and dedication to one another. After the appearance of Nikhil's radical and revolutionist friend, Sandip, the wife of silent, rational Nikhil gets attracted towards him. She is fascinated with his dynamic personality, oratory and ardent patriotic feelings and enters into relationship with him.

Likewise in the movie '*Astitva*' directed both in Marathi and Hindi deals with triangular relationship and extra-marital affairs. Aditi is a middle-class wife, has healthy (not in a true sense) love relationship with her husband Shrikant. Although he is not a brute, but treats her as a chattel, sets dos and don'ts for her. Always leaves her alone nearly for months to get settled in his business. She feels lonely and abandoned, gets infatuation for her music teacher and has physical relationship which fruits into conceiving a baby.

In both the movies, it is the wife who is prone to the situation of obsession for the need of another man physically and emotionally. In case of '*Ghare-Baire*' the wife Bimala leans towards Sandip getting haunted with his Swadeshi movement, dynamic personality and enchanting oratory. While in '*Astitva*' the wife Aditi gets attracted towards Malhar sheerly nostalgic of emotional and physical needs.

In both the cases there is an illusion of love and ideal man. The illusion lasts for few moments. In '*Astitva*' it is just momentary. And follows by realization in the respective lives. After realization of infidelity the wife repents and pines for emotional security.

Dissimilarities in the Movies

Though the theme vacillates between love triangles, extra-marital affairs and adultery, still there exist some differences and dissimilarities between the two. They are as follows:

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- In *Ghare-Baire*, there is a political and national background. While in '*Astitva*' there was not any national and political background.
- '*Ghare-Baire*' is based on novel written by Rabindranath Tagore. '*Astitva*' is not based on any novel.
- In Bengali movie, the husband is silent, rational, benevolent and of modern views. But in Hindi movie the husband is chauvinist, egoist and suspicious.
- Wife, Bimala is attracted due to intellectual needs. Here the wife, Aditi is attracted for physical and emotional needs.
- The third person, Sandip being dynamic tries to fascinate the wife and take undue advantage of her. While Malhar, the third person, not very dynamic has no such intentions.
- In '*Ghare-Baire*' the wife is accepted back by the husband after adultery. In '*Astitva*' wife is denied of the entrance again in husband's life.
- The third person in Bengali movie robs the wife in monetary terms. In Hindi movie, the third person leaves huge property in the wife's name.

Comparison of Characters of the movies

Nikhil V/S Shrikant

In spite of the same themes and triangular relationships the characters of the movies differ in their moods, temperament and outlook.

In the movie '*Ghare-Baire*' the main character Nikhil is very silent, rational and modern. He loves his wife very much, keenly wants her to learn modern and English ways of life. He is gentle and of soft nature. He insists his wife to learn modern and English ways of life. He insists his wife to tread into outside world, have interaction with other men. Nikhil can be called as dynamic because he wants his wife to come out of purdah into the outside world. He convinces her that he will never know if she really loves him unless she has opportunity to meet others and prefer him over other men. When she flirts with Sandip, Nikhil silently and patiently waits for her returning back to him. He says;

“The passage from the narrow to the larger world is stormy. When she is familiar with this freedom, then I shall know where my place is. I discover that I do not fit in with the arrangement of the other world, then I shall not quarrel with my fate, but silently take my leave- Use force? But for what? Can force prevail against Truth?” (45)

So, Nikhil is humanitarian, altruistic, honest and idealistic.

On the other hand, the main character of the movie '*Astitva*', Shrikant Pandit is an egoist, male Chauvinist man. He opines that a wife is meant for household chores only. When Aditi asks his permission for a job, he gets hurt and says that no woman in his family ever worked and he is able to give her comfortable life. He dominates their married life. Though he often has one-night stand with other women outside the station, he goads Aditi mercilessly for her infidelity. When the registered letter arrives in the name of Aditi, he himself opens it. This action was much to Megna's chagrin, their family friend. This shows his male chauvinistic attitude. He is egoist in a sense that he cannot take up the news of betrayal by his wife. So, he asks her to discontinue spousal relationship, though he realizes the fact that he is an impotent man.

In contrast to silent, kind, mature and benevolent Nikhil, Shrikant is restless, suspicious, dominating, egoist man.

Bimala V/S Aditi

Both the main female characters of the movies share the same dais and indulge into adultery though not deliberately. In case of Bimala, she has a lovable husband but not enough radiant and radical in her views. She then gets attracted towards a radical, dynamic and good orator and men related to the movement, Sandip. In the beginning Bimala is happy with her domestic sphere and confined to the traditional female role. She develops romantic feelings for Sandip and starts taking interest in Swadeshi Movement. In the beginning Bimala is the epitome of truly devoted Indian wife. She says;

“I would cautiously and silently get up and take the dust of my husband’s feet without waking him, how at such moments I could feel the vermilion mark upon my forehead shining out like the morning star.” (11)

But after her affair with Sandip, she is a changed woman. She even takes her husband’s money to finance Sandip’s lavish life-style in the name of Swadeshi Movement. After realization of her fault, she repents and confess everything to her husband, who welcomes her back in his life whole heartedly with open arms. So, the two facet of her character is been depicted in the movie.

In contrast to Bimala, Aditi is consistently a representative of submissive Indian wife. She is a quintessential middle-class wife. She is often relegated to kitchen affairs and upbringing of the child. Her husband though not a wife-beater dominates her. She takes all his moods, temperament and ego stoically. Being alone she pines for emotional and physical needs. Her sister’s lovely married life often fuels her desire of longing for love. So, in a very weak moment she succumbs to the bodily pleasures, but get out of it the very next day. After realizing her

folly Aditi even asks her teacher to stop visiting her any more. When she conceives, she tries to reveal the truth to her husband also.

After enduring the abandonment from her husband's side, she decides to leave her family. She is subject to the hatred not only of her husband but also of her son, Aniket. She is a spokesperson of a modern liberated woman who wants to search her identity.

Sandip V/S Malhar

There is a distinguishing contrast in the characters of Sandip and Malhar. Sandip is a radical, dynamic, cunning person who in the name of Swadeshi Movement even lures other people. he has been presented as parasite. He robs people to suffice his lavish life-style. He has many affairs. He falsely portrays himself as a patriot. He tries to seduce Bimala also. By his stunning speech he enchants others including Bimala. He has wrong and vile intentions. He misguides youth of India in the name of 'Bande Matram'.

Contrarily, Malhar Kamat, a music teacher is noble hearted person with good intentions. He tries his best to teach a good music to Aditi. He doesn't want to betray anyone. It is Aditi who gets fascinated towards him. He only tries to comfort her. After Aditi asks him to leave her alone and not to visit again, he never comes. But he knows the fact that it is his baby only. So, at the time of his death he nominates Aditi as heiress of his huge property.

So, Malhar is just an opposite to the character of Sandip.

About the movie 'Astitva'

The movie 'Astitva' is applauded very much and won world acclaims especially by young generation. The film won the National Film Award for Best Feature Film in Marathi in 2000, recognizing its impact and quality. The movie was praised for its bold storytelling, strong performances, and relevance.

Denouement

Both movies end with absolute diametrically opposite climaxes. In the movie 'Ghare-Baire' the marital and spousal relationships are strong enough that Bimala is forgiven by her husband and they unite again together. Aditi in 'Astitva' is not forgiven by her husband Shrikant and is left all alone leading a lonely life.

Conclusion

Marital bliss lies in the faith and emotional security which a person he or she expects and has for the spouse. Infatuation and obsession for the opposite sex is the normal tendency in a person. In both the movies, 'Ghare-Baire' and 'Astitva' the cheater not directly and deliberately gets attracted towards the third person but in an expectation of getting something which is absent in his or her spouse. To maintain the conjugal harmony a strong maturity and insight is expected. Both the movies have same themes with few differences. Setting periods are different. They have different climaxes. The reader can analyze the situations, mentality of the characters and thus the themes.

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